

Predictive Analytics in Preventive Care

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Chapter 1: Program Title and Background

Title: *PrevenTech* – Predictive Analytics for Hypertension Prevention in Rural Bangladesh

Hypertension, frequently known as high blood pressure, is a leading contributor to global morbidity and mortality and a significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Its asymptomatic progression and frequent underdiagnosis causes it to be labeled as a “silent killer”. In rural communities like Bangladesh, structural barriers – like socioeconomic disadvantages, limited healthcare infrastructure, and geographical isolation – exacerbates delays in diagnosis and treatment, thereby increasing the risk of complications. These disparities highlight the critical need for targeted, preventive interventions.

Research emphasizes the importance of early detection, and predictive analytics – a data-driven approach employing algorithms to identify pre-symptomatic at-risk individuals – offers a promising solution for early intervention in reducing the mortality rates (Van Calster et al., 2019). Predictive analytics is defined as the use of machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence (AI) to build predictive algorithms that make individualized diagnostic or prognostic risk predictions. These are based on patient-specific characteristics beyond population-level data averages, to guide evidence-based interventions for patients identified by the algorithms. Particular risk factors – such as age, body mass index (BMI), dietary habits, physical activity, and family history – can be leveraged through data modeling which will be explained throughout the report to produce timely tailored healthcare interventions to patient profiles.

“PreventTech” proposes the development and implementation of a predictive analytics model aimed at improving hypertension screening and prevention efforts in underserved rural settings. By aligning this approach with a health equity perspective, the intervention aims at addressing upstream determinants of health and reducing disparities in cardiovascular outcomes through data-informed health service.

Chapter 2: Community Health Needs Assessment Strategy (CHNA)

This program adopts a mixed-method approach, aligning with the PRECEDE-PROCEED Model. Quantitative primary data is collected through a cross-sectional survey of 20 close-ended questions. They address key predictors of hypertension including, demographics, behavioral risk factors, dietary patterns, accessibility of care, and self-reported blood pressure status. The distribution method of the survey is via physical paper forms in local clinics and digitally to support equitable participation across users with various levels of digital literacy. Interviews will be conducted with community health workers and high-risk individuals to provide contextual insight into environmental challenges. The questionnaire would consist of the following categories:

1. **Demographic:** Age group, gender, education level, occupation, income level.
2. **Lifestyle:** Frequency of physical activity, tobacco use, alcohol consumption.
3. **Stress Factors:** Self-reported stress level and stress coping mechanisms.
4. **Dietary Intake:** Frequency of fruit/vegetable intake, sodium intake, consumption of processed food, and hydration.
5. **Health Status:** Family history of CVD, previous hypertension diagnosis, frequency of blood pressure checks.

To reduce sampling and selection bias, the sample will be stratified by age and gender. Furthermore, to ensure ethical compliance, protocols will be set in place regarding informed consent, data anonymization, and secure data storage (Davidson, 2017). This CHNA is methodologically comprehensive, integrating social, epidemiological, behavioral, and environmental diagnostics to capture factors that influence hypertension. Moreover, it aligns with the Bangladesh MICS 2019 data, which covers self-reported hypertension, disability, stress, nutrition, and household conditions observed in rural environments (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). The PRECEDE model's criteria for comprehensive diagnosis is met by integrating both individual behaviors and environmental constraints. According to the MICS, 28% of adults aged >35 were told by HCP they had hypertension, though many lack access to regular screening outside urban centers; rural residents also report elevated risk factors (UNICEF, 2020). Overall, this contributes to the comprehensiveness of this CHNA. In regards to potential gaps – such as response bias and limited digital access – these are addressed through the chosen data collection method and community-based sampling.

Hypertension is prioritized due to the asymptomatic way it presents itself and its high disease burden in rural populations (WHO, 2021). It often goes unnoticed until complications arise such as myocardial infarction or CVD. By implementing predictive analytics, it facilitates earlier detection through cost-effective intervention. This approach not only supports the model's equity-driven principles but also aligns with sustainable strategies for chronic disease prevention and improved cardiovascular health outcomes.

Chapter 3: Logic Model

Inputs	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes
<p>Survey Data and Health Records (E.g. MICS 2019) to provide evidence-based risk indicators to inform the target population. These datasets ensure that the predictive model reflects real-world conditions.</p>	<p>Develop and test predictive analytics models which use local risk factor data – such as diet, stress levels, BMI – to predict individual hypertension risk to guide early intervention.</p>	<p>Number of individuals screened (blood pressure (BP) measured) which reflects the program’s reach and operational scale. It also provides baseline data for evaluating program reach and effectiveness.</p>	<p>Short-term outcomes involve increased identification of individuals at risk for hypertension and greater public awareness of the condition and its contributing factors. As more people participate in screenings and community education, early recognition of risk becomes more common.</p>
<p>Public health experts and data scientists to develop predictive algorithms. They bring domain expertise to test and refine the predictive model. Their role also includes making sure the tool is robust and ethically appropriate.</p>	<p>Conduct hypertension screenings in rural communities like Bangladesh. This can be done by facilitating on-site screening in local clinics or screening camps in various areas using portable equipment and trained local health workers.</p>	<p>Number of high-risk individuals identified to demonstrate the model’s effectiveness in targeting prevention efforts; guiding targeted interventions and referrals.</p>	<p>Intermediate outcomes demonstrate enhanced individual health behaviors such as increased physical activity, healthier diet, and regular BP monitoring in rural communities. All in all, this will help reduce any risk before the onset of severe complications.</p>
<p>Community health workers (CHWs) in administering screenings and surveys. They bridge the gap between the program and rural residents.</p>	<p>Train CHWs in digital tools, hypertension indicators, and referral processes. Training ensures consistency and quality in data</p>	<p>Number of CHWs trained indicates the program’s workforce capacity. Well-trained CHWs ensure sustainable implementation and follow-up.</p>	<p>Long-term outcomes include reduced prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension and decreased incidence of related cardiovascular</p>

	collection.		disease complications in the rural population.
Funding to cover the program costs such as training, data processing, community outreach, and implementation. Financial backing can be acquired from NGOs or public health sectors 1	Host campaigns for health education and awareness to improve health literacy and community understanding of hypertension. These activities improve the occurrence of screening and follow-ups.	Number of awareness events and attendees shows the level of community engagement and measures the extent of community outreach. These events build trust, increase knowledge, and enhance participation in preventive care.	Sustainable impact includes improved health equity by prioritizing underserved groups and strengthened local capacity for data-driven preventive healthcare.

Chapter 4: Evaluation Plan

The objective is to determine whether “PrevenTech” was implemented as intended, but also whether it achieved measurable improvements in early detection, health behaviors, and hypertension-related outcomes; what was specified in the outcomes column of chapter 3.

The evaluation will be guided by four primary questions which are: Was the predictive analytics model implemented and used as intended? Did the program increase early identification of individuals at high risk for hypertension? Were there measurable improvements in hypertension-related knowledge and behaviors? Did the intervention lead to improved health outcomes such as increased screenings or reduction in undiagnosed cases?

A cross-sectional design will be used to monitor the consistency of implementation. Key performance indicators (KPIs) include the number of CHWs trained, the number of individuals screened using the predictive tool, and attendance at awareness sessions/campaigns. Surveys and administrative data will be analyzed to identify if the activities went according to plan and reached the intended population. CHW feedback will also be collected to identify challenges in using the model and delivering follow-up care.

A pre-post design will evaluate changes in participant outcomes over time. Surveys and screening data will be analyzed to assess changes in blood pressure monitoring frequency, knowledge of hypertension risk factors, and adoption of healthier behaviors (e.g., reduced salt intake, increased physical activity). Outcome KPIs include the percentage of high-risk individuals who received follow-up care and the rate of undiagnosed hypertension before and after implementation.

The success of “PrevenTech” will be measured by increased early detection of high-risk individuals, enhanced health literacy among the community, and a measurable reduction in undiagnosed hypertension cases. All evaluation data will be broken down by gender, age, and geographic subregion to assess the program’s impact on health equity. Throughout the evaluation process, strict adherence to ethical standards—including informed consent and data confidentiality—will be maintained. Findings from “PrevenTech” can pave the way for future improvements and support the potential expansion of the intervention.

Chapter 5: Summary

“PrevenTech” proposes a community-centered, data-driven intervention aimed to improve hypertension detection and prevention in rural Bangladesh through predictive analytics. Rooted in the PRECEDE-PROCEED model, this initiative integrates epidemiological evidence, local data, and community engagement to identify individuals at risk for hypertension before symptoms arise. A mixed-method CHNA ensures contextual accuracy by combining survey data, environmental factors, and stakeholder insights. The logic model defines the resources, interventions, and projected outcomes across short-, medium-, and long-term timelines, supporting a scalable and sustainable implementation process.

Evaluation of the program will involve both process and outcome measures to assess integration, effectiveness, and health equity impact. By leveraging predictive tools, the initiative aims to promote early identification of high-risk individuals, improve community health literacy, and reduce the burden of undiagnosed hypertension. All activities are centered around ethical research practices and a commitment to equity-focused public health strategies.

Overall, “PrevenTech” represents an innovative approach to chronic disease prevention, merging technological tools with community-based care. Its successful implementation could serve as a model for future interventions targeting non-communicable diseases in underserved populations.

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